

Forced Degradation Studies, Method Development and Validation Of RP-HPLC Method for The Analysis of Endoxifen Citrate in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

Gokulapriya A.^{1*}, Vetrichelvan T.², Murugan S.³

¹M. Pharm student, ²HOD cum Dean Research, ³Associate professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy, Melmaruvathur-603319, Tamil Nadu, Affiliated to The Tamil Nadu Dr. M. G. R. Medical University, Chennai-600 032, India

ABSTRACT

Novelty: A new, stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for the first time for Endoxifen citrate estimation in bulk and tablet formulations, including comprehensive forced degradation studies. **Objective:** To develop and validate a simple, accurate, and precise RP-HPLC method for quantification and stability assessment of Endoxifen citrate. **Method:** Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Phenomenex C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) using methanol, acetonitrile, and water (60:30:10 v/v/v, 0.1% TEA) at 1.0 mL/min, with detection at 243 nm. Validation followed ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, and forced degradation was carried out under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reduction, and thermal conditions. **Results:** The retention time was 4.3 min, linearity was 16–80 μg/mL ($r^2 = 0.9998$), recoveries were 99.62–100.16%, and %RSD <1.5%. Significant degradation occurred under acidic stress, confirming stability indication. **Conclusion:** The proposed RP-HPLC method is simple, accurate, precise, and stability-indicating, ideal for quality control and stability studies of Endoxifen citrate.

Keywords: Endoxifen citrate, RP-HPLC, Forced degradation, Validation, ICH guidelines, Pharmaceutical dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

Z-endoxifen is a tamoxifen metabolite with antiestrogenic activity. Tamoxifen is converted in endoxifen in liver by CYP_{2D6} enzyme. Thus, patients with low CYP_{2D6} enzyme activity could have lower drug concentrations when treated with tamoxifen. As matter of fact, pharmacogenetic analyses of tamoxifen trials showed an association between treatment efficacy and reduced cytochrome P₄₅₀ 2D₆ (CYP_{2D6}) metabolism or low endoxifen concentrations. Moreover, in vitro studies showed that Z-endoxifen inhibited tumour growth more potently than tamoxifen [1]. The phase I study of endoxifen in women with endocrine refractory mBC revealed Z-endoxifene to be safe and well tolerated. Furthermore, it was unaffected by cytochrome P₄₅₀ 2D₆ (CYP_{2D6}) metabolism. A randomized phase II clinical trial comparing Z-endoxifen with tamoxifen in women with mBC has been recently completed. Z-endoxifen

was not significantly superior to tamoxifen, although a longer PFS was observed in the experimental arm for patients not previously treated with CDK_{4/6i} [2].

The chemical name of Endoxifen citrate is a 4-[(E)-1-[4-[2-(methylamino) ethoxy] phenyl]-2-phenylbut-1-enyl] phenol citrate which contain triphenylethylene derivative (active metabolite of tamoxifen), containing phenolic, ether, and tertiary amine groups [3]. The amine is protonated with citric acid to form a stable, water-soluble citrate salt, suitable for oral administration. Endoxifen (a weak base due to the dimethyl amino group) reacts with citric acid to form a citrate salt. It increases Water solubility, Chemical stability, Bioavailability for pharmaceutical use [4][5][6].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Endoxifen citrate

On literature survey, several methods were reported for the estimation of Endoxifen individually and in combination with other drugs. So, we have developed a method should be simple, rapid, accurate, precise and highly sensitive RP-HPLC method for the estimation Endoxifen citrate in tablet dosage form according to ICH guidelines. The developed method was validated as per ICH norms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation:

The analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with an LC-20AD, a UV-Visible detector, and Lab Solutions software, employing a Shimadzu C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.5, 5 μm). An electronic balance (Shimadzu AUX-220) was used for weighing, while sample sonication was performed using a Sonicator. A hot air oven (InfraDIGI, up to 250 °C) and a UV light chamber were utilized for stability and degradation studies.

Reagents and Chemicals:

All chemical and reagent of HPLC graded were purchased from Qualigens India Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India. The pharmaceutical dosage form used in this study was Zonalta tablet was purchased from Apollo pharmacy, Chennai contains equivalent to 8 mg of Endoxifen citrate per tablet and API of Endoxifen citrate was supplied from API pharmaceuticals. HPLC grade of Acetonitrile, HPLC grade of Methanol, HPLC grade of water, 0.1% Triethylamine, 0.1N Sulphuric acid, 1% Hydrogen peroxide, 10% Sodium bisulfate, 0.1N Potassium hydroxide was used.

METHOD OPTIMIZATION

The chromatographic method was optimized by systematically varying different parameters, including mobile phase composition, detection wavelength,

diluent and flow rate, to achieve sharp, symmetric peaks with suitable retention time and resolution.

Mobile phase Optimization

Various combinations of water, methanol, and acetonitrile, with and without acidic modifiers, were tested. Mobile phases without modifiers resulted in peak broadening and tailing. The inclusion of 0.1% triethylamine significantly improved peak symmetry and reproducibility. The final optimized mobile phase consisted of methanol, acetonitrile and water (60:30:10 v/v/v) containing 0.1% triethylamine, which produced sharp, symmetric peaks with an acceptable retention time.

Selection of Diluent

Methanol was used as the diluent.

Selection of Wavelength

The UV spectrum of Endoxifen was recorded in the range of 200–400 nm. The drug exhibited maximum absorbance at 243 nm, which was selected as the detection wavelength since it provided maximum sensitivity with minimal baseline noise.

Optimization of Flow Rate

Flow rates in the range of 0.5–1.5 mL/min were evaluated. At higher flow rates, resolution decreased, while at lower flow rates, analysis time was prolonged. A flow rate of 1.0 mL/min was found to provide a balance between resolution and analysis time and was selected as optimal.

Final Optimized Condition

The optimized chromatographic conditions included a Phenomenex C₁₈ column (4.5 × 250 mm), a mobile phase of methanol, acetonitrile and water (60:30:10 v/v/v) containing 0.1% triethylamine, flow rate of 1.0 mL/min, UV detection at 243 nm, and an injection volume of 20 μL. These conditions produced sharp, symmetric peaks with acceptable system suitability parameters, fulfilling ICH requirements.

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Preparation of standard stock solution

Accurately weighed quantity of Endoxifen is equivalent to 80 mg was transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark.

Preparation of working standard solution

Pipetted out 2.5 ml from that standard stock solution and diluted to 50 ml using methanol to get working concentration of 160 µg/ml.

Preparation of sample stock solution

20 Tablets of formulation (ZONALTA) containing 8 mg of Endoxifen was weighed accurately. The average weight of tablets was found and powdered. The tablet powder of Endoxifen equivalent to 8 mg was weighed and transferred into 50 ml volumetric flask and added a minimum quantity of Methanol to dissolve the substance by using sonicator for 15 minutes and made upto mark using methanol to get a sample stock solution of Endoxifen. The content was filtered through the Whatmann filter paper No.41. Pipetted out 2 ml taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask made up to the volume with Methanol to get concentration 32 µg/ml is a sample solution. The procedure was repeated for 6 times for each concentration.

METHOD VALIDATION ^{17]}

The proposed methods were validated as per ICH guidelines.

System Suitability

System suitability was assessed by injecting the standard solution under optimized conditions. Endoxifen produced a sharp, symmetric peak at 4.300 min. Theoretical plates were >2000, and the tailing factor was <2.0. These values indicate good column efficiency and peak symmetry. All parameters complied with ICH acceptance criteria.

Linearity

Different aliquots of 1.0 - 5.0 mL of working standard solution was transferred into series of 10 mL volumetric flasks, separately and the volume was made up to the mark with methanol to get concentrations 16, 32, 48, 64 and 80 µg/mL, respectively.

Accuracy

Accuracy was determined by calculating recovery of Endoxifen by the standard addition method. Known amounts of standard solutions Endoxifen (16, 32, 48 µg/ mL) were added to get percentage about 50%, 100% and 150% with a prequalified test solution of Endoxifen (32 µg/ mL). Each solution was measured in triplicate, and the recovery was calculated by proposed method.

Precision

(a) Repeatability

The solution was prepared by pipetting out 2 ml of the working standard solution (160 µg/ mL) into 10 mL volumetric flask and the volume was adjust to mark with methanol. This solution (32 µg/ mL) was determined for 6 times. The solutions were analysed by proposed method and calculate % RSD.

(b) Intra-day precision

Intra-day precision was determined by analysing solution (32 µg/ mL) for six times on the same day. The results were reported in terms of %RSD.

(c) Inter-day precision

Inter-day precision was determined by analysing the solution (32 µg/ mL) for six times on the different day. The results were reported in terms of %RSD.

Robustness

The Robustness was evaluated by wavelength, flow rate and mobile phase ratio. During studies of Robustness there was not much change retention time, and symmetry of peak. The effect of changes was found to be with in the acceptance criteria. The %RSD should be less than 2%.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness of the proposed method is determined by analysed the aliquots from homogeneous slot by two analyst and two instrument using different operational and environmental conditions.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

They were measured using standard deviation of Y-intercept and slope of calibration curve as per ICH guideline. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using following formula

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / s$$

Where,

σ = the standard deviation of response

s = the slope of the calibration curve

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES ^{[8][9][10]}

Acid degradation

Acid degradation studies were performed by transferring 2 mL of working standard solution in to 10 mL of volumetric flask. 2 mL of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs. After time period 2 mL of 0.1 N KOH Added to neutralize the solution and make up the volume with diluent.

Base degradation

Base degradation studies were performed by transferring 2 mL of working standard solution in to 10 mL of volumetric flask. 2 mL of 0.1 N KOH solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs. After time period 2 mL of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ Added to neutralize the solution and make up the volume with diluent.

Oxidation degradation

Oxidation degradation studies were performed by transferring 2 mL of working standard solution in to

10 mL of volumetric flask. Two mL of 1 % H₂O₂ solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs. After time period make up the volume with diluent.

Reduction degradation

Reduction degradation studies were performed by transferring 2 mL of working standard solution in to 10 mL of volumetric flask. 2 mL of 10 % sodium bisulfate solutions was added and mixed well and kept for 24 hrs. After time period make up the volume with diluent.

Thermal degradation

Thermal degradation studies were performed by transferred accurately weighed quantity of Endoxifen (raw material) was equivalent to 80 mg (previously kept in Hot air oven for 24 hrs at 70°C) into 25 mL volumetric flask made up the volume with diluent (methanol). Diluted with 2.5mL of above solution in to 50 mL of volumetric flask and made up the volume with diluent. Further, pipetted out 2 mL from the above solution into the 10 mL volumetric flask and made up the volume with diluent. Inject the solution into the HPLC system.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION

The HPLC procedure was optimized with a view to develop a suitable LC method for the determination of Endoxifen citrate in tablet dosage form. Initially, methanol, acetonitrile and water in different ratios were tried that is shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Mobile phase selection

S.NO	Mobile phase composition	Interference
1	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (60: 25: 15) v/v/v	Peak splitted, improper baseline and negative side of elongation
2	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (20: 40: 40) v/v/v	Peak eluted with improper baseline fluctuations
3	Water: Methanol: acetonitrile (40: 30: 30) v/v/v with 0.1% formic acid	Peak eluted with more baseline noise and appears negative peak also
4	Methanol: water (80: 20) v/v with 0.1% triethylamine	Peak eluted with void peak and delayed RT: 7.883 mins
5	Methanol: acetonitrile: water (60: 30: 10) v/v/v with 0.1% triethylamine	Sharp peak eluted with expected time RT: 4.300 mins (Optimized chromatogram)

Optimized chromatogram**Fig 3: Optimization peak with mobile phase Methanol: acetonitrile: water (60: 30: 10) v/v/v with 0.1% triethylamine****METHOD VALIDATION**

The described method has been validated which include parameters like system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOD (limit of detection) and LOQ (limit of quantification).

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

System suitability and chromatographic parameters were validated such as tailing factor and theoretical plates was calculated. The results are given in table 3.

Table 2: System suitability parameters.

PARAMETERS	ENDOXIFEN CITRATE
Retention time	4.3 mins
Peak area	1633895
Theoretical plate	8757.68
Tailing factor	1.019

Linearity

The method showed excellent linearity with the regression equation $y = mx + c$ and a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9998$), confirming its suitability for quantitative analysis. The data are given in **Table 3**. Calibration curves were constructed in the concentration range of 16-80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ is shown in **figure 4**. The optical parameters, including correlation coefficient, slope, intercept, LOD, and LOQ, are given in **Table 4**.

Table 3: Linearity graph of Endoxifen

S.NO	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area
1	16	816947
2	32	1633895
3	48	2425356
4	64	3233976
5	80	4108219

Fig 4: Linearity graph of Endoxifen**Table 4: Optical characterization**

SI.NO	Parameter	Endoxifen
1	Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	16-80
2	Regression equation ($y = mx + c$)	$Y = 51042x - 5290$
3	Slope (m)	51042
4	Intercept (c)	5290
5	Correlation co-efficient (R^2)	0.9998
6	SE of intercept	16698
7	S. D	4090
8	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10.7656
9	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	8.0331

PRECISION

System precision was assessed by six replicate injections of 32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Endoxifen. The % RSD of 0.13040 was within acceptable limits, confirming the method's precision (Table 5, Figure 5).

Table 5: Precision of Endoxifen

Precision	Label claim (mg/tab)	Amount found (mg)	% Purity	% Average	SD	% RSD
1	8	8.01	100.12	100.185	0.13065	0.13040
2		8.03	100.37			
3		8.00	100.00			
4		8.02	100.25			
5		8.01	100.12			
6		8.02	100.25			

Accuracy

Accuracy was evaluated by the standard addition method at three concentration levels, each analyzed in

triplicate. The mean % recovery of Endoxifen was within acceptable limits, confirming the accuracy of the proposed method (Table 6)

Table: 6 Recovery studies of endoxifen

Sample	% Conc	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount spiked (µg/ml)	*Estimated amount (µg)	*Recovered amount (µg)	*Average % recovery	SD	%RSD
END	50	32	16	47.94	15.94	99.62	1.3021	1.3068
	100	32	32	64.10	32.1	100.31	0.1322	0.1317
	150	32	48	80.08	48.08	100.16	0.5838	0.5827

*Mean of 3 observations (n=3)

Robustness

Robustness was assessed by making deliberate variations in flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min), wavelength (\pm

1 nm), and mobile phase composition (± 1 mL). The % RSD values remained within acceptable limits, demonstrating that the method is robust. The robustness results are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Robustness of Endoxifen

PARAMETER	AMOUNT FOUND (mg)	% PURITY*	SD	% RSD
FLOW RATE				
0.9 ml/min	7.99	99.87	0.7125	0.7127
1.0 ml/min	8.006	100.07	0.7788	0.7780
1.1 ml/min	8.01	100.12	0.3750	0.3745
MOBILE PHASE COMPOSITION				
Methanol: ACN: H ₂ O (61: 28: 11, %v/v/v) with 0.1% triethylamine	7.983	99.78	0.3818	0.3826
Methanol: ACN: H ₂ O (60: 30: 10, %v/v/v) with 0.1% triethylamine	8.03	99.78	0.6898	0.6871
Methanol: ACN: H ₂ O (59: 32: 09, %v/v/v) with 0.1% triethylamine	7.96	99.5	0.1931	0.1939
WAVELENGTH				
242 nm	8.02	100.25	0.1931	0.1925
243 nm	7.97	99.62	0.2193	0.2201
244 nm	7.98	99.75	0.4413	0.4420

*Mean of 3 observations (n=3)

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was evaluated under varied conditions, with % RSD values within acceptable limits,

confirming good reproducibility. The results are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Ruggedness of Endoxifen

Sample	Types of ruggedness	*Average % recovery	SD	%RSD
Endoxifen	Analyst 1	99.78	0.3818	0.3826
	Analyst 2	99.53	0.2886	0.2899
	Instrument 1	99.74	0.7207	0.7225
	Instrument 2	100.16	0.3818	0.3811

*Mean of 3 observations (n=3)

Forced degradation studies

Forced degradation studies were carried out to evaluate the stability of Endoxifen under different stress conditions. The drug showed notable degradation only in acidic environments, whereas it

was stable under alkaline, oxidative, reductive, and thermal conditions. These findings demonstrate that the developed RP-HPLC method is capable of detecting degradation and can be considered stability-indicating. The results are given in Table 9 and the chromatograms are shown in Figures 6-10.

Table 9: Forced degradation of Endoxifen

Stress condition	Time(h)	% degradation
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	24	70.86
0.1M KOH	24	Not degraded
Oxidation	24	Not degraded
Reduction	24	Not degraded
Thermal	24	Not degraded

Figure 10: Chromatogram for Thermal degradation study

CONCLUSION

The stability-indicating HPLC method was developed, validated according to ICH guidelines and was applied for the determination of Endoxifen citrate in tablet formulation. The results obtained from validation studies revealed that, the developed method was found to be rapid, simple, accurate, precise, specific, selective and economical. Results obtained from the force degradation, indicates that in acidic condition drug were considerably degraded. Overall, the proposed RP-HPLC method is reliable for routine quality control analysis of Endoxifen citrate in pharmaceutical formulations, as well as for stability testing during formulation development

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared none.

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